

Machine Learning Approaches for Social Media Based Depression Detection: A Review

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Abstract

Depression is one of the most prevalent mental health disorders that affect millions of individuals and leading to severe psychological, social and economic consequences. Traditional diagnosis of depression relies mainly on clinical interviews and psychological assessments. However, recent advances in machine learning, natural language processing (NLP) and physiological signal analysis have enabled automated detection of depression using social media data and bio-signals. This review summarizes current computational approaches for depression detection, focusing on machine learning models with textual and physiological data sources. It also discuss data sources, feature extraction techniques and algorithms used in depression detection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Depression is a serious mental health disorder characterized by persistent sadness, loss of interest in activities and reduced cognitive functioning. It can affect personal relationships, professional life and overall well-being. Worldwide, depression affects millions of people and is considered as a leading cause of disability [1].

Traditional depression diagnostic approaches typically rely on psychological assessments, clinical interviews and self-reported questionnaires. However, these methods depend heavily on patient honesty and therapist's expertise, which may lead to delayed diagnosis or misclassification [2]. Therefore, the researchers have begun exploring computational techniques to detect depression.

The rapid growth of social media platforms have created new avenue for mental health research. Individuals frequently express emotions, experiences and psychological struggles on social media platforms such as Twitter and Reddit. These digital footprints provide valuable insights into emotional and behavioral patterns that can be analyzed using machine learning techniques [3].

Recent studies have demonstrated that the linguistic features such as behavioral indicators and physiological signals can be used to identify depressive patterns [4],[5],[6]. As a result, machine learning depression detection has become an unavoidable technique in latest researches.

Global Impact of Depression

Depression affects individuals across all age groups without the classification of socioeconomic backgrounds. According to global health statistics, approximately 5% of adults in worldwide experience depression each year [1]. Depression may lead to reduced productivity, impaired social functioning and increased risk of suicide. Recent researches identified that many adults who have depression remains untreated [7]. This highlights the importance of developing early detection systems to identify individuals at risk.

Data Sources for Depression Detection

Data for depression detection may be collected from emotional, behavioral, cognitive and physiological behaviour of the individuals. Different types of information may collect and analyze to identify depressive patterns using computational methods. In recent years, apart from physiological information, social media data become most influencing factor in identifying the chance of depression.

Social Media Data

Social media platforms have become valuable data sources for studying mental health conditions. Now a days, the users frequently share their personal thoughts, emotions and daily experiences online, which can reflect their psychological state. De Choudhury et al. [8] demonstrated that the behavioral signals from Twitter posts, such as reduced social engagement and increased negative sentiment, can indicate early signs of depression. Similarly, the studies of Ren et al. [9] in Reddit communities have shown that the emotional and linguistic patterns in posts are revealing depressive symptoms. Thorstad and Wolff [10] also found that the everyday language patterns on social media can predict future mental illness even before the clinical diagnosis.

Physiological Data

The physiological signals such as electroencephalogram (EEG) recordings have been used to detect depression. EEG measures electrical activity in the brain and provides insights into neurological patterns associated with mental disorders. Avots et al. [11] developed an ensemble learning approach that uses EEG features to detect depression with high accuracy. Similarly, Shen et al. [2] proposed an improved empirical mode decomposition method to extract meaningful features from EEG signals for depression classification.

Feature Extraction Methods

Feature extraction in depression analysis state the techniques which are used to identify suitable raw data from various sources and transform them into useful numerical features. These selected and converted features can be used to train or test the machine learning model to detect depressive patterns. The possible features are classified as linguistic, behavioral and physiological.

Social Media Linguistic Features

Text-based depression detection systems commonly rely on linguistic and semantic features. It includes word frequency, emotional tone, sentiment polarity, pronoun usage and cognitive style indicators. Researches shows that the individuals with depression often use absolutist words such as “always,” “nothing,” and “completely,” reflecting cognitive distortions associated with depressive thinking [12].

In [13], a machine learning-based analysis of psychiatric interview texts are used for emotional pattern identification, particularly expressions related to disgust and sadness. The model

achieved a high area under curve (AUC) score of 0.85. The study concluded that incorporating emotion-specific features can significantly enhance the performance of depression detection systems in clinical settings.

The authors [14] found that the depression influences various linguistic and structural aspects of text, including sentence complexity and coherence. Unlike traditional binary classification, this approach identified specific depressive symptoms from textual data.

H. Wang et al. [15] analyzed emojis and emoticons to determine meaningful emotional signals that contribute to better detection performance. The integration of emotional embeddings into a Text Graph Convolutional Network (TextGCN) model significantly improved classification accuracy. The study concluded that the emotion-aware deep learning models are essential for improving robustness in social media based depression detection.

In [16], lexicon based approaches are applied to social media data and revealed that the depressed individuals often use more negative and self-focused language. Although these methods are computationally simple and interpretable.

S. Gupta et al. [17] developed text based depression detection system using natural language processing techniques with an average accuracy of 80%. The variations in accuracy depends on the type of textual data. In their conclusion, clinical interview transcripts tend to produce more reliable results compared to social media text due to structured and context-rich information.

In [18], L. Smith et. at developed context-aware NLP models to detect depression even in the absence of explicit keywords by analyzing semantic relationships and contextual cues. These models outperform traditional keyword based systems.

A Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) based text summarization approach [19] improved depression detection by reducing noise and focusing on key semantic content. The model achieved an F1-score of 0.81, indicating strong performance in depression analysis.

A large-scale study using BERT and BERTopic models on mobile generated text data demonstrated a strong correlation between textual responses and patient health questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) depression scores. The findings indicate that continuous monitoring of user-generated text can support early identification of depressive symptoms. The study concluded that mobile based NLP systems can be effectively used for real-time mental health screening [20].

Topic modeling techniques such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI) and Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) were used by D. Patel [21] to identify depression related themes in textual data. These methods were effective for analyzing long content messages such as essays and narratives. However, topic modeling is valuable for uncovering hidden psychological patterns in text.

Social Media Behavioral Features

Social media behavioral indicators for depression identification are the engagement on social media and activities such as posting frequency, engagement levels and interaction patterns. Individuals experiencing depression often show decreased social interaction and reduced online activity [8].

Research using smartphone behavioral data [22] demonstrated that the features such as screen time, app usage frequency and communication patterns detected depression with an accuracy of approximately 87%. Individuals with higher depression scores showed reduced social interaction and increased passive phone usage. According to the authors, smartphone-based behavioral monitoring is a scalable and cost effective approach for continuous mental health assessment.

In [23], a smartphone sensor related study made to identify behavioral factors such as diet regularity, sleep timing and daily physical activities as a key predictors of depression. This model achieved accuracy of 73.11% to 88.24% and found that the depressed individuals exhibited irregular lifestyle patterns and lower activity levels. Therefore, the passive sensing of daily behavioral routines can effectively support early detection of depression in real world environments.

T. Mullick et al. [24] conducted an adolescent-focused study using mobile sensor data and found that the behavioral features including call logs, screen usage and location patterns are suggestively contributed to depression prediction. Personalized models improved accuracy when compare to generalized models, highlighted individual variability in behavioral patterns. However, incorporating personalized behavioral profiles enhanced the effectiveness of depression detection systems.

A study by J. Wang et al. [25] demonstrated the influence of social interaction features such as engagement level, emotional influence and network behavior in depression identification and they have achieved an accuracy of 77%. Similarly, İ. Baydili et al. [26] reported accuracy ranging from 80.74% to 99.96% by integrating posting behavior, emotional expression and activity patterns with feature selection techniques, emphasizing the effectiveness of hybrid behavioral linguistic models.

Transformer-based approaches have improved the performance. B. G. Bokolo and Q. Liu [27] achieved 97–98.1% accuracy using contextual behavioral indicators such as posting frequency and emotional tone. In another research, A. Malviya et al. [28] analyzed Reddit user behavior including temporal posting patterns and interaction trends. This analysis achieved up to 98% accuracy.

M. K. Myee et al. [29] explored on emotional intensity as a behavioral marker. They found that the patterns of sadness, anger and fear contribute significantly to determine depression. This early detection helps to reinforce the role of affective behavior. Z. Chen et al. [30] proposed a hybrid temporal model known as Sentence-BERT (SBERT)-Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) by modeling user behavior over time. The proposed model achieved 86% accuracy. In 2022, H. E. Tay et al. [31] introduced the Speech Emotion Recognition Convolutional Neural Network (SERCNN) model, which discussed chronological posting behavior and achieved 93.7% accuracy. In this model, limited behavioral sequences were also used to reveal depression trends. A. Reece and C. Danforth [32] analysed behavioral indicators such as posting frequency, engagement and visual attributes on Instagram and reported 70% accuracy in prediction.

Physiological Features

EEG-based depression detection models typically extract features such as spectral power, fractal dimension and signal complexity. These features capture nonlinear characteristics of brain activity that are associated with depressive states.

A study using EEG-based nonlinear features such as Higuchi Fractal Dimension (HFD) and Sample Entropy demonstrated in [33]. This research achieved an accuracy ranging from 90.24% to 97.56% across multiple machine learning models. These features effectively captured brain signal irregularities associated with depression. Therefore, EEG-derived nonlinear physiological features are highly sensitive biomarkers and reliably distinguished depressed individuals from healthy controls.

E. Avots et al [11] used an ensemble learning approach with EEG physiological features such as spectral and nonlinear measures and achieved classification accuracy of 90% using Support

Vector Machine (SVM) and K- Nearest Neighbor (K-NN). The study found that the combination of different EEG features improved robustness and classification consistency.

A multimodal physiological system in [34] integrated with EEG and Electrocardiogram (ECG) signals, achieved a classification accuracy of 92.6%, with a peak performance of 94.7% using SVM. Key features included theta/alpha brainwave ratios and heart rate variability (HRV). This study shows that the combination of multiple physiological signals improved depression related cognitive detection and enables effective real-time monitoring system. Similarly, S. K. Sharma et al. [35] made a research on physiological signal based frameworks using EEG and ECG. It demonstrated a strong effectiveness in detecting mental stress.

A deep learning model developed by D. K. J. B. Saini et al. [36] by combining EEG and ECG physiological features, achieved an accuracy of 93% and AUC of 0.96 in classifying emotional and depressive states. The model significantly outperformed traditional machine learning methods and so the hybrid CNN-Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) architecture was highly effective for physiological depression detection.

Studies using EEG wavelet and nonlinear features [37] reported very high classification accuracies up to 99.58%, depending on feature extraction and classifiers. These physiological features captured significant differences in brain activity between depressed and healthy individuals.

A multimodal physiological study by A. Patil and A. N. Paithane [38] combined EEG and ECG signals and achieved an accuracy of 98.6% (feature-level fusion) and 97.8% (score-level fusion), outperformed individual sensor models (EEG: 96.6%, ECG: 91.79%). The findings shown that the physiological signal fusion significantly enhanced detection performance.

A study by L. Simorgh et al. [39] analysed heart rate variability (HRV) and cortisol levels of the individuals. It demonstrated that HRV effectively classified physiological stress responses linked with depression. The findings shown a strong correlation between HRV patterns and cortisol levels in stress activation.

A review conducted by M. Gjoreski et al [40] on physiological monitoring techniques revealed that the features such as HRV, Electro Dermal Activity (EDA) and EEG signals are consistently associated with depression and stress detection. These features provide objective and quantifiable measures compared to traditional assessments.

Machine Learning Approaches

Traditional Machine Learning

Early depression detection systems used classical machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machines, Random Forest, Naive Bayes and K-Nearest Neighbor. These models rely heavily on manually engineered features and have shown promising results in detecting depression from questionnaire data and social media posts [41].

A. Prayoga, R. Wahdiniwaty, and D. S. Wanggur [42] made a comparative study of Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Naive Bayes for the detection of depression from social media text. SVM performed with an accuracy of 92.93% and precision of 93%, while Naive Bayes achieved 79.01% accuracy. SVM effectively captured complex patterns in depressive expressions and so, as a traditional machine learning model, SVM is more efficient for early depression detection in textual data.

In [43], a Naive Bayes model is used for the prediction of depression among university students. The model achieved 78.03% accuracy with strong sensitivity in identifying moderate and severe depression cases. It effectively classified the level of depression with behavioral and demographic features.

W. Chen et al. [44] applied multiple traditional machine learning algorithms such as Random Forest, SVM and Naive Bayes in their study and identified that the Random Forest and Neural Networks outperformed with an accuracy of 86.8%. In this study, the demographic factors such as age and education meaningfully influenced depression prediction.

M. Hassan et al. [45] made a study on depression detection by using SVM, Nave Bayes and maximum entropy classifiers. SVM, Naive Bayes and Maximum Entropy achieved accuracy of 91%, 83% and 80% respectively.

A large-scale study [46] using SVM, Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes were made by Y. Liu et al. In results, different models were excelling in different evaluation metrics and so the authors concluded that the models are reliable but, based on the objective (precision vs recall) it is required to select the model.

Deep Learning Methods

Deep learning models have significantly improved depression detection performance by automatically learning complex representations from large dataset. Common architectures include convolutional neural networks (CNN) and recurrent neural networks (RNN).

Orabi et al. (2018) used deep neural network architectures to detect depression from Twitter data and demonstrated improved performance compared to traditional machine learning models. Similarly, Ren et al. (2021) proposed an emotion based attention network that captured emotional semantic information from Reddit posts and achieved high detection accuracy.

D. Pakkattil and R. S. Devi [47] developed CNN–BiLSTM deep learning model and it was applied to EEG signals for depression detection. This model effectively captured both spatial and temporal brain signal patterns and demonstrated very high classification accuracy with 99.02% (left hemisphere) and 98.06% (right hemisphere).

A framework generated by M. A. Rahman et al [48] integrated CNN and LSTM with facial expression dataset. It captured complex behavioral and emotional patterns of individuals and achieved accuracy of 94% and AUC of 0.96.

An attention based BERT–CNN–BiLSTM model [49] incorporated emoji features and achieved accuracy of 97.12% and AUC of 91.23%. The model identified emotional patterns such as negative emoji usage in depressed users.

In [50], CNN–Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) model applied to EEG signals to classify depressive and nondepressive state. The model effectively captured temporal dependencies and spatial features of brain with an accuracy of 98.74%.

A model with CNN and LSTM was developed by D. K. J. B. Saini et al. [51] for physiological signal analysis. This model effectively classified emotional and depressive states using EEG and ECG data, and achieved an accuracy of 93% and AUC of 0.96.

S. Gupta et al. [52] performed a comparative deep learning study using CNN, audio CNN and Bi-LSTM models. The audio features performed well with an accuracy of 98% for audio CNN, 92% for textual CNN and 88% for Bi-LSTM. The study highlighted that the CNN-based models are highly effective especially in audio data.

Transformer-based Models

Recent studies have introduced transformer architectures such as Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) for depression detection. These models capture contextual relationships between words more effectively than traditional deep learning models. Qasim et al.[53] demonstrated that the transformer-based models can classify depression severity levels from social media posts by analyzing subtle contextual and emotional cues. In a deep learning study [54], hybrid CNN-LSTM models outperformed standalone CNN models,

with an overall accuracy of above 91%, while transformer-based models achieved up to 93.33% accuracy.

A hybrid deep learning model [55] with Sentence-BERT (SBERT) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) was developed for depression detection from social media posts. This model effectively captured semantic and contextual features from user generated text and achieved an accuracy of 0.86 and F1-score of 0.86, outperformed earlier machine learning models.

A transformer-based study [56] compared the performance of models such as RoBERTa and LSTM, demonstrated better contextual understanding. It produced an accuracy of 93.22% for RoBERTa and 92.65% for LSTM. In depression related text analysis, the transformer-based deep learning models outperformed traditional RNN-based architectures.

In S. Malviya et al. [57], Reddit data is used to train the models such BERT, RoBERTa and XLNet, and achieved up to 98% accuracy in depression detection. This study concluded that the transformer architectures are highly effective due to their ability to capture contextual and semantic nuances in text.

In [58], BERT based depression detection model is trained with 20,000 text samples. The model effectively classified depression into multiple severity levels and the accuracy of training phase was 95.5% and testing accuracy was 92.2%.

A. Qasim et al. [59] made a study on depression severity classification using RoBERTa and achieved 100% accuracy in training and 90% in validation. This model effectively classified depression cases into mild, moderate and severe.

A hybrid transformer-based model [60] combined BERT with CNN for text and image analysis. The integration of contextual textual features and visual cues significantly improved detection performance and achieved 99% accuracy, outperformed standalone BERT (97%) and CNN (89%).

J. Garcia et al. [61] developed an encoder-only transformer model (DEENT-BERT) for analyzing complex linguistic patterns associated with depression and achieved 84.54% accuracy. It surpassed traditional ML models such as Random Forest (80.17%) and SVM (80.63%), as well as deep learning models like CNN and RNN (80%).

In [62], DistilBERT model is used with metadata and linguistic features, and achieved F1-score of 84.15%, improved from 72.59% after applying data augmentation. This study highlighted that the incorporation of auxiliary features enhanced model performance.

A cross attention model (MacBERT with multimodal fusion) [63] effectively integrated multiple data modalities using attention mechanisms and achieved an accuracy of 94.95%. This study concluded that the cross-attention in transformer architectures enhanced contextual understanding and improves depression detection accuracy.

The comparison of transformer models such as BERT, RoBERTa, ALBERT and ELECTRA with LSTM is made by K. Hasan et al. [64]. RoBERTa achieved the highest performance across all classes with an accuracy and F1-score between 91% and 99%. This study states that the transformer-based models are more appropriate for depression detection due to their superior contextual representation capabilities.

Challenges and Ethical Issues

Although computational approaches are promising effective identification strategy for depression, several challenges remain. First, analyzing personal social media data raises privacy concerns. Ethical guidelines must be followed when collecting and analyzing sensitive mental health data. Second, many dataset rely on self-reported diagnoses, which may have biases and inaccuracies. Lack of standardized datasets, limited generalizability across populations are also the difficulties in this research. Finally, models trained on data from specific platforms may not generalize well to other populations or cultural contexts.

Furthermore, no single modality is sufficient for fully reliable depression detection, as each approach captures only partial aspects of the disorder.

2. CONCLUSION

In depression detection, computational approaches have evolved significantly from traditional machine learning methods to advanced deep learning and transformer-based models in terms of improved performance accuracy and reliability. Text-based approaches shows that the linguistic patterns, sentiment and contextual semantics are strong indicators of depression, while transformer models such as BERT and RoBERTa enhanced performance by capturing deeper contextual relationships. Behavioral feature systems, smartphone usage, sleep patterns and physical activity demonstrated predictive capabilities. Physiological signal based methods such as EEG, ECG and heart rate variability, provide the highest accuracy levels. Traditional machine learning models such as SVM, Naive Bayes and Random Forest remain reliable baseline approaches with accuracies between 70% and 98%, though they are limited in handling complex and unstructured data. In contrast, deep learning models, including CNN, LSTM and hybrid architectures, outperform traditional methods by effectively capturing spatial, temporal and multimodal patterns with above 90% accuracy.

Future Research Directions

Future research should focus on developing multimodal depression detection systems that combine textual, behavioral and physiological data. Additionally, explainable artificial intelligence methods should be incorporated to improve model transparency and trustworthiness in clinical settings. Privacy-preserving and culturally adaptive machine learning techniques, such as federated learning, may also help to address ethical concerns related to sensitive mental health data.

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